

applied as a foliar application at booting and 10 d later. We measured ShR incidence as a percentage of tillers affected on 25 randomly selected hills/plot, 20 d after the last spray.

In the first trial, applying gypsum to the soil in two equal splits at different

times was comparable with carbendazim in reducing ShR and increasing grain yield significantly (see table). Foliar application of the salts was inferior to the gypsum application.

In the second trial, all gypsum treatments significantly reduced ShR, al-

though only basal applications increased the yield considerably.

Gypsum is a promising treatment for reducing ShR incidence in rice and for increasing grain yield when applied as two equal splits. ■

Integrated pest management—insects

Effects of botanical treatments on brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål)

I. F. Telan, T. H. Xuan, and F. M. Olivares, Jr., Crop Protection Division, Philippine Rice Research Institute, Maligaya, Muñoz, Nueva Ecija, Philippines

We tested several extracts from plant species for use in controlling brown planthopper (BPH).

Field-collected BPH populations were cultured in screenhouse insect cages. Sap was extracted from test botanicals using a mortar and pestle and then mixed with water (1:1). Three-week-old TN1 seedlings/pot (7.6-cm-diam) were kept in a screened enclosure. Leaves were pruned at 30 cm above soil level.

Each extract (4 ml/pot) was applied to rice seedlings using a hand sprayer.

Immediately after treatment, about 900 nymphs (4th-5th stages) and adults (3:1) were released and prorated in the enclosure. We counted BPH on the plants after 12 h.

The free-choice experiment was laid out in a completely randomized design replanted twice for each treatment, and replicated five times. Endosulfan-treated and untreated rice plants served as controls.

Some of the botanical treatments were significantly more effective than others, but none were nearly as effective as endosulfan (see table). Untreated plants had the most insects (8.6/plant). Nymphs and adults responded in the same way to treatments. *Azadirachta indica*, *Anonas reticulata*, and *Tinosphora rumphii* appear to have repellent effects on BPH. ■

Effects of botanical treatments on BPH.

Plant species/ chemical	Plant part used	BPH/ plant ^a (no.)
Endosulfan ^b	-	0.5 a
<i>Anonas reticulata</i>	Leaf	3.6 b
<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	Leaf	4.0 bc
<i>Tinosphora rumphii</i>	Vine	4.6 bcd
<i>Capsicum frutescens</i>	Fruit rind	6.0 bcde
<i>Pithosporum resiniferum</i>	Leaf	6.3 bcde
<i>Carica papaya</i>	Leaf	6.5 bcde
<i>Dieffenbachia picta</i>	Leaf, stalk	6.5 bcde
<i>Momordica charantia</i>	Leaf, stem	6.5 bcde
<i>Anonas muricata</i>	Leaf	6.8 bcde
<i>Curcuma zedoaria</i>	Rhizome	7.1 bcde
<i>Citrus</i> sp.	Leaf	7.6 de
<i>Ageratum conyzoides</i>	Leaf	7.8 de
<i>Anonas squamosa</i>	Leaf	8.1 de
<i>Catharanthus roseus</i>	Leaf	8.6 e
<i>Musa sapientum</i>	Stalk	8.6 e
Control	-	8.6 e

^aMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^bThree tablespoons/16 liters of water.

Research methodology

Illustrating the recommendation domain concept in integrated pest management: an Indian case study

H. M. Singh, Entomology Department, Narendra Deva University for Agriculture and Technology (NDUAT), Kumarganj, Faizabad 224229, Uttar Pradesh, India; R. K. Srivastava, Plant Pathology Department, NDUAT; R. K. Singh, Office of the Director for Research, NDUAT; and S. Savary, Institut Francais de Recherche Scientifique pour le Développement en Cooperation (ORSTOM)-IRRI Shuttle Project, IRRI

Integrated pest management (IPM) strategies are site-dependent. Among the many reasons for this is that the particular combination of pests and diseases (the injury profile) that affects a given crop is, to a significant extent, driven by location-specific crop management practices. Another reason is that the amount of yield reduction (damage) that can be attributed to a given injury profile depends on the (attainable) yield the crop would have achieved had these pests been absent. The attainable yield reflects a given production situation and is site-

dependent. It is therefore necessary to identify the domains where rice pests and diseases may become constraints to productivity and where differing IPM strategies are to be considered.

Surveys have been jointly initiated by NDUAT, IRRI, and ORSTOM since 1991 to characterize the injury profile associated with differing production situations in Uttar Pradesh, India. The surveys address monsoon season crops in three typical rainfed landforms of two villages. The procedure to analyze this information is exemplified using 1992 data, represent-